

ATOMIC PARACHOR OF COPPER

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Parachor of copper has been determined from the study of a covalent compound, copper acetoacetate. The value 40 is of the same order of magnitude as obtained from fused copper and copper chloride in methyl alcohol. It is again confirmed that the parachor of a substance in dissolved state is lower than in pure state.

Atomic parachor of copper from its compounds has not been determined. Smith and Sugden (Sugden, "Parachor and Valency", p. 198) have determined its atomic parachor in a fused state. The values obtained by them are 44.8 and 47.0 respectively. In view of the very high temperature (m.p. of copper) used in determining surface tension and density, the results need verification as the results might not be reliable. The best way therefore to determine the parachor is from the study of the parachor of copper chloride (anhydrous) in methyl alcohol where there is little chance of ionisation.

TABLE I
Parachor of cupric chloride in methyl alcohol.

$x(\text{CuCl}_2)$	Temp.	d	r	P_m	P_x
0.04343	22.3°	0.9311	29.82	91.85	152.4
"	25.0°	0.9283	29.54	91.65	154.0
"	30.0°	0.9234	28.34	91.51	150.8
0.06585	21.8°	1.006	33.39	93.12	154.8
"	25.0°	1.000	33.63	93.34	158.1
"	30.0°	0.9961	32.87	93.21	156.2
0.08390	21.3°	1.0530	35.45	94.24	153.2
"	25.0°	1.0500	36.04	94.54	156.8
"	30.0°	1.4800	35.68	94.65	158.0

Assuming that cupric chloride does not ionise in methyl alcohol, the parachor of copper can be calculated as follows:—

$$P_{\text{Cu}} = P_{\text{CuCl}_2} - 2 P_{\text{Cl}}$$

The average value of P_{CuCl_2} is 153. The value for $2P_{\text{Cl}} = 2 \times 54.3 = 108.6$. Hence the value of parachor of copper is $153 - 108.6 = 44.4$. This value is in excellent agreement with that obtained for molten copper.

We also prepared the copper salt of ethylacetoacetate, which like similar well known compounds of other metals is a non-electrolyte.

The copper in this compound has a co-ordination number of four. The dotted arm according to modern theory represents a semipolar bond, both the electrons being donated by oxygen atom in each case. On the ground that the polar link between oxygen and copper makes oxygen positively charged and copper negatively charged,

which is contrary to the accepted principle, Sugden suggested redistribution of electrons in such compounds assuming that links are formed by singlets and triplet instead of duplets of electrons. This would make all the atoms neutral, but this would give only four electrons to copper, which is equally unsatisfactory.

It is interesting to find what light is thrown on the two suggested constitutions from the study of parachor of copper ethylacetoacetate in CHCl_3 , as solvent. The results are as follows.

TABLE II

α (Copper acetoacetate).	Temp.	d .	τ .	P_m .	P_z .
0.02554	23.3°	1.4730	26.45	195.2	603.2
0.01781	20.6°	1.4750	28.05	191.9	601.0
0.01860	20.2°	1.4710	27.37	192.3	602.2

On average the value of copper ethylacetoacetate may be taken as 602.2 ΣP omitting copper for $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{O}_3)_2 = 295.2 \times 2 = 590.4$. This gives the value for copper as $602 - 590.4 = 11.6$. This is abnormally low as compared to the values obtained from fused copper and anhydrous copper chloride in methyl alcohol, the value being $P_{\text{Cu}} = 44.0$. If singlet or triplet formulae are used, the value of $\Sigma P = 272 \times 2 = 544$, and hence the value of $P_{\text{Cu}} = 602 - 544 = 58$. The value is higher than 44 but approaches it to a greater extent than the value 11.6 obtained from semipolar structure of copper acetoacetate.

The above method used by us on the lines of Sugden needs criticism. Sugden has used this procedure in case of beryllium salts and thallos salts. According to him the structure of the type (I) may change either to (II) or (III) or (IV) (cf. "Parachor and Valency," p. 143). In calculating ΣP Sugden has assumed the structure (III) and not the (IV) which is actually neutral. ΣP of the fourth structure for $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{O}_3)_2$ is not 272. There is no justification for this procedure. The objection to formulae (III) can be raised on the ground that one oxygen is positive and other is negative, contrary to the fact that oxygen can be negative only. Further, Sugden has compared his values ("Parachor and Valency," p. 145) with those obtained from the compounds which are salts. It is well known that the binding in salts is electrovalent and not covalent. The values therefore obtained for electrovalent compounds cannot be compared with those in which metal is covalently linked. The parachor of thallium calculated in this way by Sugden is not justified. It is a general observation that the parachor of a substance in a solvent is generally lower than in the pure state. In case of ethylacetoacetate the same was observed and the value in benzene is much lower than the calculated value ($P_{\text{obs.}} = 298$ and $P_{\text{calc.}} = 306$). The value of parachor of copper acetoacetate in chloroform therefore must be lower than that of the substance in pure liquid form. It is suggested therefore that there is no justification in substituting calculated ΣP of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{O}_3)_2$ in the observed value of copper acetoacetate in chloroform. The value to be considered should be one which is comparable, that is in solution. This value is 298 and hence $P(\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{O}_3)_2 = (298 - 17.2) \times 2 = (280.9) \times 2 = 561.8$, the value of P_{Cu} therefore is $602 - 561.8 = 40.2$, which is in good agreement with the values obtained for molten copper and for P_{Cu} from anhydrous cupric chloride in methyl alcohol.